

COMPARISON OF SELECTED PSYCHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS AMONG DIFFERENT PLAYING POSITIONS IN FOOTBALL

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Abstract:

This study under investigation involves the comparison of selected psychological parameters among different playing positions in football. Thirty six college level male football players between 18 and 25 years of age group (mean age = 21.45 ± 0.8 years) studying in various colleges around Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala were selected as subjects. Among the thirty six players 12 were defenders, 12 were midfielders and 12 were attackers. Anxiety was assessed by Rainers Marten's Questionnaire and the standard psychological tool devised by M. L. Kamalesh was used to assess the sports achievement motivation. Analysis of variance and scheffe's post hoc test were used. In all the cases, 0.05 level of confidence was fixed to test the significance, which was considered as an appropriate. It was observed that there were insignificant differences in anxiety among football players at various playing positions. It was observed that attackers having high sports achievement motivation among football players than the other position players.

Key Words: Anxiety, Achievement Motivation, Football.

Introduction:

Sports psychology is a specialization within psychology that seeks to understand psychological/mental factors that affect performance in sports, physical activity and exercise and apply these to enhance individual and team performance. It deals with increasing performance by managing emotions and minimizing the psychological effects of injury and poor performance. Some of the most important skills taught are goal setting, relaxation, visualization, self-talk awareness and control, concentration, using ritual, attribution training, and periodization. Sports competitions today occupy the prime of place in human life, because, it is the testing ground for the human excellence almost without the aid of scientific and technological assistance, but for the implements, exhibiting the performance of body-mind co-ordination and system synchronization of sources and efforts. Competition is a specialized situation where the athletes fight for supremacy and excellence. World records are being rewritten every now and then, as the present day's athletes prove to be stronger, faster and more efficient than the past ones, and most probably, in future the athletes may prove still better. The main reason for such an estimate is the advancement in science and technology on one side and the scientific training on the other, especially the psychological based training and the selection of right type of sports. It is believed that sports are a psycho-social activity full of tension, anxiety, fear, strain and stresses. In competitive sports, sports persons play to win and this spirit of winning causes many psychological stresses. The resource generation, systematization of resources developed, utilization of resources in appropriate context in required quantum, running into conflicts or the resolution of conflicts and decision making are to be done in split seconds in various sports situations, which depend on the personality adjustment of the athlete and the team to which he belongs to. Teams may win or lose under psychological stress. It is believed that winning an international sports competition greatly depends on the psychological abilities. Therefore superb psychological fitness and training of the individual are the factors which help in achieving outstanding performance (Silva & Weinberg, 1984).

Anxiety is often seen as a triggering of the fight-or-flight reaction, causing excess adrenaline to be produced by the adrenal glands, which in turn produce other hormones (catecholamines) that affect various parts of the body, such as heartbeat and respiration. Anxiety is in reality a relationship occurring through time between a person and the situation he or she faces. It can be referred to as the behavioural and physiological responses directly induced by a situation (Hallam, 1992). Specific symptoms of the anxiety expectation includes heart palpitation, disturbances of respiration, sweating, tremor and shuddering, vertigo and other physiological and behavioral manifestations (Freud, 1924). Anxiety is distinguishable from other unpleasant affective state (emotional) such as anger, grief, or sorrow by its unique combination of phenomenological and physiological qualities. This gives to anxiety a "character of displeasure" which although difficult to describe seems to possess a particular note of its own (Onestak, 1991).

The meaning of achievement motivation has been a controversial subject and a topic of key interest to psychologists. The concept of achievement motivation appears in almost every theoretical account of behavior. Motivation is a mental event, which determines the course of action. Motivation is used to consider any inner conditions of the organism that initiates or directs its behavior towards a goal. By motivation we mean conditions within the organism that activate behavior and influence its direction. Motivation is the driving force that causes the flux from desire to will in life. For example: a flower with no water still desires for water to

sustain life; however, due to its incapability to move and get water, the flower cannot will for water, hence, suffering from a break in the driving force of motivation; it is not to say, however, that, necessarily, the flower lacks the driving force; therefore, all life can said to have, at its very minimal, the igniting spark of motivation. It can be considered a psychological state that compels or reinforces an action toward a desired goal. For example, hunger is a motivation that elicits a desire to eat (Claudio & Laura, 2007).

Methods:

This study under investigation involves the comparison of selected psychological parameters among different playing positions in football. Thirty six college level male football players between 18 and 25 years of age group (mean age = 21.45 ± 0.8 years) studying in various colleges around Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala were selected as subjects. Among the thirty six players 12 were defenders, 12 were midfielders and 12 were attackers. Anxiety was assessed by Rainers Marten’s Questionnaire and the standard psychological tool devised by M. L. Kamalesh was used to assess the sports achievement motivation.

Statistical Analysis:

Analysis of variance and scheffe’s post hoc test were used. In all the cases, 0.05 level of confidence was fixed to test the significance, which was considered as an appropriate.

Analysis of Data:

The procedure of testing the hypothesis in accordance with the results obtained in relation to the level of confidence which was fixed at 0.05 level, was considered necessary for this study. The tests are usually called as the test of significance, since we test whether the difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the samples are significant or not. In the present study, if the obtained F-ratio was greater than the table F-ratio at 0.05 level, the hypothesis was accepted to the effect that there existed significant difference between the means of groups compared. And if the obtained, t-ratio was lesser than the table t-ratio at 0.05 level, then the hypothesis was rejected to the effect that there existed no significant difference between the means of groups under study. The probability level below which, we reject the hypothesis, is termed as the level of significance. The F-ratio obtained by Analysis of variance needed for significance at 0.05 level.

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of Selected Psychological Parameters of Football Players at Various Playing Positions

S.No	Variables	Mean Values with SD		
		Defenders	Midfielders	Attackers
1	Anxiety	19.08±3.55	20.25±3.88	19.66±4.14
2	Sports Achievement Motivation	29.91±2.11	22.66±2.87	32.41±1.87

Table 2: One Way Analysis of Variance for Anxiety among Football Players at Various Playing Positions

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Means Squares	F	T.F
Between Groups	8.16	2	4.08	0.27	3.28
Within Groups	493.83	33	14.96		

The table 2 shows the one way analysis of variance of anxiety levels among football players at various playing positions. From the table 2, it was very clear that the obtained F-ratio was 0.27 and table F-ratio was 3.28. As the obtained F-ratio was lesser than the table F-ratio, the study was insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degree of freedom 2 and 33.

Figure 1: Figure Showing the Mean of Anxiety among Football Players at Various Playing Positions

Table 3: One Way Analysis of Variance for Sports Achievement Motivation among Football Players at Various Playing Positions

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Means Squares	F	T.F
Between Groups	615.50	2	307.75	6.60*	3.28
Within Groups	1538.50	33	46.62		

The table 3 shows the one way analysis of variance of sports achievement motivation levels among football players at various playing positions. From the table 3, it was very clear that the obtained F-ratio was 6.60 and table F-ratio was 3.28. As the obtained F-ratio was greater than the table F-ratio, the study was insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degree of freedom 2 and 33.

Table 4: Scheffe's Test for Difference between the Pairs of Means of Stress among Football Players at Various Playing Positions

Positions	Mean Values	Mean Difference		
		Defenders	Mid-Fielders	Attackers
Defenders	29.91	--	7.25*	2.51
Mid-fielders	22.66	--	--	9.76*
Attackers	32.42	--	--	--

The critical value was 6.38. The attackers sports achievement motivation level was higher than the defenders and midfielders. The defenders sports achievement motivation level was higher than the attackers. The attackers and defenders were having same level of sports achievement motivation.

Figure 2: Bar Diagram Showing the Mean of Sports Achievement Motivation among Football Players at Various Playing Positions

Conclusion:

- It was observed that there were insignificant differences in anxiety among football players at various playing positions.
- It was observed that attackers having high sports achievement motivation among football players than the other position players.

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